

Geographical Analysis on the Role of Drinking Water Suppliers in Pathein City

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Abstract

The research paper “Geographical Analysis on the Role of Drinking Water Suppliers in Pathein City” analyses the type of water sources used by the people of Pathein that supply drinking water based on the available water resources such as purified drinking water plants and water vendors. Pathein city, the capital of Ayeyarwady region, is located in the delta region. The main aim of the study is to describe the role of drinking water suppliers in Pathein. In this study, the two types of data – primary data and secondary data are used. Primary data are collected by the methods of interview and field survey. Secondary data are toposheets, records from various purified drinking water plants, departmental reports, and research papers through which location, local climate, hydrogeology, population, water sources, and available resources for drinking water are studied. The required amount of daily drinking water for the people of Pathein is 474516 liters and 145000 liters (31%) of that amount is provided by the 6 purified water plants. It was found that water vendors supply 229460 liters, 48 % of City’s requirement in the summer and 73700 liters (16%) in the rainy season. According to the finding of this study, it is suggested that it is necessary to have a water supply system that may be usable to people of different social status and that is hygienic for the people since the price of drinking water is four times higher than that of the neighboring countries.

Key Words: Drinking Water, Drinking Water Supply System, Purified Drinking Water

Introduction

The earth where we live is a satellite in which water and air play an important role for the survival of the organisms. Although 70% of the surface of the earth is covered by water, there is no sufficient amount of fresh water to drink for human beings. As estimated by WHO, due to the lack of purified water and inadequate health education, more than 5 million people suffer disease and die every year. So, the availability of purified drinking water plays a vital role. Purified drinking water is such kind of water that contains no harmful insects and chemicals but it is hygienic and has the level of pH 7. Since the amount of water consumption for each individual is different, the type and source of used by the people of Pathein is also different. This study emphasizes the main source that supply for the people of Pathein from the geographic point of view. It also chiefly presents the role of water suppliers of Pathein by title of the role of purified water plants and water vendors.

Study Area

Among the regions of self-autonomy in the Union of Myanmar, Ayeyarwady is a region that is important for the economy of the country. Pathein, the capital city of Ayeyarwady region, 30 miles far from the coast is the third largest port city after Yangon and Mawlamyine. The population of Pathein in 2014 was 158172, which was the 5th most populated city in Myanmar after Yangon, Mandalay, Mawlamyine, and Bago. There are 15 wards in Pathein, which is 61 sq kilometers (24.49 sq miles). Monsoon rain is the main source for agricultural and drinking water in Ayeyarwady Region. Rain water, surface water and ground water are the

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water recourses for Pathein. Some amount of drinking water in Pathein is supplied by rain water as well as ponds. In the summer, tube wells, brick-lined wells and purified drinking water factories are primary suppliers of drinking water for the City residents.

Aim

The main aim of the study is to describe the role of drinking water suppliers in Pathein City.

Objectives

The objectives of this study are; 1.To describe sources of water in Pathein City 2.To study the distribution of purified drinking water plants in Pathein City, 3.To find out the distribution of tube wells and brick-lined wells that the water vendors use, 4.To present the amount of water supplied by water vendors and purified drinking water plants for urban population.

Methods

Primary data are collected by interview and field survey. By using Microsoft Excel, in the form of graphs that depict the rise and fall of daily and yearly water production of purified drinking water plants and the amount of water produced each day in the Summer and in the Rainy Season from tube wells and brick-lined wells. Buffer analysis is used to present accessibility of purified drinking water for city residents.

Findings

The finding of the study using questions administered to 100 families that have at least 2 to at most 8 family members showed that drinking water consumption for each individual per day is 3 liters. In 2014, the population of Pathein City was 158172, the amount of water consumption for the whole city was 474516 liters. In 2015, purified drinking water plants supplied 145000 liters (31%) of water for the people in Pathein City.

People living in ward Nos. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 11, 12, 14, 15 situated on the Eastern bank of the Pathein river use water produced by purified drinking water plants. Among these wards, 90% of the household use purified drinking water in ward No.4; 40 to 70 % in ward Nos. 2, 3, 6, 7, 13, and 15; 30 to 40 % in ward Nos.11, 12, and 14; 10 to 30 % in ward Nos.1 and 8. Ward No. 9 situated on the West bank uses 9% of household but ward No. 10 does not use drinking water at all. In these wards, the use of drinking is little because of their income level, due to having own tube well, using water from the brick-lined wells in their wards, and using the water sold by water vendors as drinking water.

People of Pathein City use water sold by water vendors for drinking as well as domestic use. There are 172 water vendors in Pathein City who distribute drinking water from 15 brick-lined wells and 6 tube wells. Most of the brick-lined wells that supply drinking are in ward No. 9 and 10, on the west bank of the Pathein river. The brick-lined wells and tube wells in Pathein distribute 458920 liters of water for drinking and domestic use in the summer and 147400 liters in the rainy season every day. People use only 50% of the water sold by water vendors for drinking. Therefore, water vendors supply 458920 liters of drinking water for the people of Pathein, among them, 48 % (229460 liters) of drinking water in the summer and 16% (73700 liters) of drinking water in the rainy season.

According to the findings, it was found that purified drinking plants are situated in ward Nos. 5, 6, 8, and 13 and that they could not supply the daily needed amount of drinking water although they supplied 31% of drinking water that the people of Patheingyi required. It was also found that people near the water plants use more but those who live far from the water plants use little. Therefore, it is necessary to build purified drinking water plants in those wards that have none in order to supply enough water for the people of Patheingyi.

Discussion

Availability of Drinking Water

Availability of drinking water sources of Patheingyi City derive from buffer analysis with 500 meters for ponds, 1000 meters for tube well and brick-lined well, and 100 meters along the road for purified drinking water plant.

There are (5) ponds which are available for drinking water and they are located in ward No. 7, 9 and 14. In addition, brick-lined wells and tube wells which are available for drinking water are located in ward No. 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 8, 9 and 10. Drinking water for the Patheingyi dwellers is also distributed from purified water plants. Mainly, in purified water distribution 100 m (330 ft) away from each side of road which is able to be accessed by purified water carry cars is assigned and studied.

In this study, when 500 m (1650 ft) around away from these drinking water ponds, northern part of ward No. 7, and southwestern part of ward No. 14 where are located the ponds are found falling in the part of assigned to buffer zone.

Ward No. 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 8, 9 and 10 where are location the brick-lined wells, of which the most of area are falling in the tube well and brick-lined well buffer zones. Moreover, ward No. 4, 7 and 14, where no brick-lined wells have and tube wells, of which the some areas also are falling in buffer zone. Purified drinking water for the urban dwellers is mainly distributed by trucks and hand carts from the purified water plants. Most of the area of ward No. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 14 are falling within the buffer zone which is available to purified water. In these wards, found that ward No. 8, 11, 12, 13, 15 are outside the area of buffer zone, because the roads which can distribute to purified water are lack.

According to figure (1), water vendors from the wards No. 9 are found up to far more than distance assigned from buffer zone which is mainly distributed of drinking water resources. It was found that there is a large area outside the buffer zone that cannot be distributed purified drinking water in ward No. 8, 11, 12, 13 and 15. The reason of having outside buffer area is that there is no street land to distribute drinking water and there is no water vendor to sell water from pond, brick-lined well and tube wells. It was found that the people who live in the buffer area have enough drinking water from brick-lined well and tube well. Thus, inhabitants of these wards are viewed using the drinking water made by owned tube wells.

Figure 1. Availability of drinking water in Patheingyi City

Source : Field Survey

Purified Drinking Water Supplier

Purified drinking water plants play important roles for the people of Patheingyi to have purified drinking water. There are six major purified drinking water plants in Patheingyi City. They are

- (1) Kaung Thant Purified Drinking Water Plant
- (2) Shwe Kathit Purified Drinking Water Plant
- (3) Khing Shwe Sin (KSS) Purified Drinking Water Plant
- (4) Nectar Purified Drinking Water Plant
- (5) Swedaw Purified Drinking Water Plant
- (6) Cho Aye Mya Purified Drinking Water Plant

These are the purified drinking water plants that mainly supply drinking water for the people of Patheingyi. In Patheingyi City, the average production amount of purified drinking water plants are not differences in rainy and summer seasons. Location of purified drinking water plants in Patheingyi City is as shown in Fig. (2).

Figure 2. Location of Purified Drinking Water Plants in Patheingyi City (2015)

Source: Field Survey

Kaung Thant Purified Drinking Water Plant that produced 26000 liters (5719 gallons) per day of purified water in 2011 increased its production to 28390 liters (6245 gallons) in 2012, 59000 liters (12978 gallons) in 2013, 80000 liters (17598 gallons) in 2014 and 2015. There are three kinds of purified drinking water bottle produced by Kaung Thant Purified Drinking Water Plant such as 20 liters, 1 liter and 0.6 liter bottles. Kaung Thant Purified Drinking Water Plant is now distributing purified water to ward No. 1, ward No.2, ward No.3, ward No.4 and ward No. 6. Moreover, this plant is also distributing purified drinking water to the shops, hotels and motels in Ngwe Saung, Chaungtha, Daga, Lapputta, Ngaputaw, and Kangyidaung. Kaung Thant Purified Drinking Water Plant sells its purified water to the customers 300 kyats for a 20 liter bottle, 750 kyats for a card of six one liter bottle, and 1100 kyats for a dozen of 0.6 liter bottle. Kaung Thant Purified Drinking Water Plant is distributing

purified drinking water to the customers 15 for 70588 liters (15528 gallons) to 17 times for 80000 liters (17598 gallons) a day by six vehicles. The amount of daily production in liter from 2011 to 2015 is presented in Fig 3.

Figure 3. Daily Production of Kaung Thant Purified Drinking Water Plant (2011-2015)

Source: Based on Table 1

Shwe Kathit Purified Drinking Water Plant, established in October 2004, is situated in ward No. 13. It is a branch of Kaung Thant Purified Water Plant. Shwe Kathit Purified Drinking Plant produces only one type of 1 liter bottles by daily production amount of 8500 liters (1870) gallons. Due to the requirement, the amount of production usually increases from 9000 liters (1980) gallons to 10000 liters (2200) gallons in April and May. Shwe Kathit Purified Drinking Water Plant that produced 6500 liters (1430) gallons per day of purified water in 2011 increased its production to 7610 liters (1674 gallons) and 8000 liters (1760 gallons) in 2013. This plant produced 8500 liters (1870gallons) in 2014 and the amount of production became 10000 liters (2200gallons) in 2015. Purified drinking water is produced by using Reverse Omission (RO) system. Shwe Kathit Purified Drinking Water is distributed directly to the customers living ward No.2, ward No. 3, ward No. 6, ward No. 13, NgweSaung, Chaungtha, Laputta and Myaungmya. This plant distributes its purified water in cheap price by selling 750 kyats for a card of 6 bottles each containing 1 liter. The amount of daily production in liter from 2011 to 2015 is presented in Fig. 4 .

Figure 4. Daily Production of Shwe Kathit Purified Drinking Water Plant (2011-2015)

Source: Based on Table 1

Khaing Shwe Sin (KSS) Purified Drinking Plant was established in ward No. 5 in 2005. It produces four sizes of bottles such as 20 liters, 1 liter, 0.6 liter and 0.3 liter by using UV (Ultra Violet) system. The amount of daily production of this plant was 10000 liters (2200

gallons) in 2011, 10997 liters (2419 gallons) in 2012 and 12000 liters (2640 gallons) in 2013 and 15000 liters (3300 gallons) in 2014 and 2015. This brand of purified water is being distributed to the customers of Patheingyi and Eime. The work of distribution is carried daily by car and two trolleys. The price is also relatively cheap for the customers because the cost of a 20 liter bottle is 300 kyats, a dozen of 0.6 liter bottle is 2000 kyats and a dozen of 0.3 liter bottle is 800 kyats. The amount of daily production in liter from 2011 to 2015 is presented in Fig. 5.

Fig 5. Daily Production of Khing Shwe Sin (KSS) Purified Drinking Water Plant (2011-2015)

Source: Based on Table 1

Nectar Purified Drinking Plant was established Ward No. 5 in May 2010. This plant produces 20 liter and 1 liter purified water bottles by using UV system. The amount of daily production of this plant was 12500 liters (2750 gallons) in 2011 and 13997 liters (3079 gallons) in 2012. Although it produced 16000 liters (3520 gallons) in 2013, the production increased to 20000 liters (4399 gallons) in 2014 and 2015.

Starting from the day of the beginning of production, the Nectar brand has increasing amount of production till now. This plant distributes its purified water in cheap price by selling 750 kyats for a card of 6 bottles each containing 1 liter. Nectar Purified Drinking Water Plant is distributing purified drinking water to the customers living in Patheingyi City ward No.2 and ward No. 3 as well as to other towns such as Ngwesaung, Chaungtha, Daga and Thabaung in retail whole sale prices by four vehicles daily. The amount of daily production in liter from 2011 to 2015 is presented in Fig. (6)

Figure 6. Daily Production of Nectar Purified Drinking Water Plant (2011-2015)

Source : Based on Table 1

Swedaw Purified Drinking Plant, established in 2010 in ward No. 8, produces 8000 liters (1760 gallons) of 20 liter bottles daily by using UV system. The amount of daily production of this plant was 6900 liters (1518 gallons) in 2011, 7997 liters (1759 gallons) in 2012-2013 and 8000 liters (1760 gallons) in 2014-15. This brand of purified water is being distributed mainly to the customers living ward Nos. 2, 6, 8, 11, 13 and 15. Moreover, it also distributes to Chaungtha, Ngwe Saung and Shwemyintin and the work of distribution is carried daily by three cars. The price of a 20 liter bottle is 300 kyats. The amount of daily production in liter from 2011 to 2015 is presented in Fig. (7).

Figure 7. Daily Production of Swedaw Purified Drinking Water Plant (2011-2015)

Source: Based on Table 1

Cho Aye Mya Purified Drinking Plant situated in ward No. 6 was established in June 2014. Cho Aye Mya brand produces 20 liter bottle and 0.6 liter bottle. Although 20 liter bottles are produced every day, 0.6 liter bottles are produced only when the donors order for them to be used in the donation ceremonies. At the moment of its establishment in 2014, due to the fact that this brand was little known among people, only 600 liters (132 gallons) of purified water was produced daily. But this plant has to produce 12000 liters (2640 gallons) per day in 2015. The UV system is used in this plant. This brand of purified drinking water is being distributed mainly to the customers living ward Nos. 3, 4 and 6. Moreover, it also distributes to the villages in Kangyidaung Township. The price of a 20 liter bottle is 300 kyats and a dozen of 0.6 liter bottle is 1200 kyats. The work of distribution is carried daily by three cars. The amount of daily production in liter from 2011 to 2015 is presented in Fig. (8).

Figure 8. Daily Production of Cho Aye Mya Purified Drinking Water Plant (2014-2015)

Source : Based on Table 1

The above mentioned six purified drinking water plants provide 145000 liters (31897 gallons) of daily drinking water for the people living in Pathein. The amount of daily production in liter from 2011 to 2015 is presented in Table No.(1), the total production of purified drinking water plants in Pathein City (2015) is present in Fig.9 (a) and Percentages of Daily Production by Purified Drinking Water Plants in Pathein City (2015) is presents in figure. 9(b)

Table. (1) Daily Production of Purified Drinking Water Plant in Pathein City (2011 to 2015)

Ward No.	Purified Drinking Water Plants	liters				
		2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
13	Kaung Thant	26000	28390	59000	80000	80000
	ShweKathit	6500	7610	8000	8500	10000
5	KhaingShwe Sin (KSS)	10000	10997	12000	15000	15000
	Nectar	12500	13997	16000	20000	20000
8	Swedaw	6900	7997	7997	8000	8000
6	Cho Aye Mya	-	-	-	12000	12000
	Total	61990	68991	102997	143500	145000

Source: Field Survey 2015

Figure 9. (a) Total Production of Purified Drinking Water Plants in Pathein City (2011-2015)

Source: Based on Table 1

Fig 9. (b) Percentages of daily production by Purified Drinking Water Plants in Patheingyi City (2015)

Source : Based in Table 1

The Role of Water Vendors

In ward No. 1, although there are 3 brick-lined wells situated in Thitnyogone monastery, only one well can be used as drinking water and the rest two wells are still in the stage of renovation to get drinking water. There are 12 water vendors in Thitnyogone brick lined well who sell 19200 liters (4224 gallons) of water every day with 12 carts 3 times a day in the summer and 4800 liters (1065 gallons) 2 times a day in the rainy season. According to the distance of the location, a 20 liter bottle is sold 100 kyats to 150 kyats in Kwanchan, Shwewahtun, Sinthiri, Ywatha, Nga Auk Chaung, Yankintaung and Shwebontha. From this well, 12 water vendors sell 19200 liters (4224 gallons) of water per day in the summer and 4800 liters (1056 gallons) a day in the rainy season.

There are 2 brick lined wells in ward No.2 : well No. 1 is situated on the Shwesigone pagoda hill and well No. 2 is near Kyaungthit monastery. In well No. 1 brick lined well of Shwehsegon, 10 water vendors sell 24000 liters (5279 gallons) of water every day with 10 carts each containing 10 buckets 15 times a day in the summer and 12800 liters (2816 gallons) 8 times a day in the rainy season. From this well, 10 water vendors sell 24000 liters (5279 gallons) of water every day in the summer and 12800 liters (2816 gallons) in the rainy season in ward No. 2 by 200 kyats a 20 liter bottle.

In well No. 2 brick-lined well of Kyaung Thit, 5 water vendors sell 6000 liters (1320 gallons) of water every day with 3 carts each containing 10 buckets 10 times a day in the summer and 3000 liters (660 gallons) 5 times a day in the rainy season. In this well, 6400 liters (1408 gallons) of water every day with 2 carts each containing 40 buckets 4 times a day in the summer and 3200 liters (704 gallons) 2 times a day in the rainy season. According to the distance of the location, a 20 liter bottle is sold 50 kyats to 100 kyats in Lati, ShweHninsi and Ngawonkyuntha. From this well, 5 water vendors sell 12400 liters (2728 gallons) of water every day in the summer and 6200 liters (1364 gallons) in the rainy season.

In ward No. 2, there are 15 water vendors selling 34600 liters (8007 gallons) of water every day in the summer and 19000 liters (4180 gallons) in the rainy season.

In ward No. 3, there is a brick lined well which is situated in the campus of No. 2 B.E.S.H. In this well, there are 4 water vendors with 3 water tanks and a trishaw. From this well, 3 water tanks each carrying 20 buckets can distribute 3200 liters (704 gallons) 8 times a day in the summer. There is no water vender in this area in the rainy season. From this well, a

20 liter bottle of water is sold by 200 kyats in ward No. 2 and ward No. 4. There are 4 water venders who sell 7200 liters (1584 gallons) of water to the customers in the summer.

There are 2 brick lined wells situated in ward No. 5. There are 12 water venders in brick lined well No. 1 who sell 24000 liters (5279 gallons) of water every day with 12 carts each containing 10 buckets 10 times a day in the summer and 14400 liters (3168 gallons) 6 times a day in the rainy season. From this well, 12 water venders sell 24000 liters (5279 gallons) of water every day in the summer and 14400 liters (3168 gallons) in the rainy season in ward No. 2 by 200 kyats a 20 liter bottle. From this well, a 20 liter bottle of water is sold by 50 kyats to those who live in Ohnmardandi Street and Pantingone Street.

There are 9 water venders in brick lined well No. 2 situated in ward No. 5. They sell 18000 liters (3960 gallons) of water every day with 9 carts each loaded 10 buckets 10 times a day in the summer and 5400 liters (1189 gallons) 3 times a day in the rainy season. A 20 liter bottle of this well is sold 50 kyats in Ohnmardandi, Panset and Papawadi quarter. These are altogether 21 water venders sell 2 brick-lined well from ward No. 5. These sell 42000 liters (9239 gallons) of water per day in the summer and 19800 liters (4355 gallons) a day in the rainy season.

There are 3 tube wells in ward No. 6. Tube well No. 1 is situated in Kuthinayon pagoda compound. In this well, there are 12 water venders who sell 14400 liters (3185 gallons) of water every day with 4 carts each loaded with 30 buckets 6 times a day in the summer and 4800 liters (1056 gallons) 6 times a day in the rainy season. There are 8 water venders who sell 14400 liters (3168 gallons) of water every day with 8 carts each loaded with 15 buckets 6 times a day in the summer and 4800 liters (1056 gallons) two times a rainy season. A 20 liter bottle of this well is sold by 50 kyats to 100 kyats in wards Nos. 2, 4 and 6 depending on the location.

From this well, water vendors distribute 28800 liters (6335 gallons) of drinking water in the summer and 9600 liters (2112 gallons) of drinking water to the customers every day.

There are 7 water venders in tube well No. 2 situated in ward No.6 who sell 15600 liters (3432 gallons) of water every day with 5 carts each contained 12 buckets 13 times a day in the summer and 7200 liters (1784 gallons) 6 times a day in the rainy season. The water of this well is sold 12480 liters (2745 gallons) per day with two 24bucket carts 13 times a day in the summer and 5760 liters (1267 gallons) 6 times a day in the rainy season. A 20 liter bottle of this well is sold by 100 kyats in ward No. 8. From this well, 11 water venders sell 16800 liters (3696 gallons) of water per day in the summer and 6720 liters (1478 gallons) a day in the rainy season.

From this tube well, a 60 gallons water cart is sold by 1200 kyats to 1500 kyats in ward No. 6 and Ward No. 4. The 7 water venders of this well sell 28080 liters (6177 gallons) of water per day in the summer and 12960 liters (2851 gallons) a day in the rainy season.

In tube well No. 3 of ward No. 6, there are 15 water venders who sell 54000 liters (1187 gallons) of water every day with 15 carts each contained 12 buckets 15 times a day in the summer and 18000 liters (3959 gallons) 6 times a day in the rainy season.

From this well, 15 water venders sell 54000 liters (1187 gallons) of water every in the summer and 18000 liters (3959) gallons a day in the rainy season.

There are 3 tube wells in ward No. 6 from which 34 water venders distribute 110880 liters (24391 gallons) of water every in the summer and 40560 liters (8922) gallons a day in the rainy season.

There are 3 tube wells in ward No. 8 from which water venders distribute drinking water to the customers every day.

There are 16 water venders in tube well No. 1 situated in ward No. 8 who sell 24300 liters (5345 gallons) of water every day with 15 carts each loaded 9 buckets 9 times a day in the summer and 5400 liters (1188 gallons) 2 times a day in the rainy season. The water of this well sold 4680 liters (1029 gallons) per day with a 26 bucket trishaw 9 times a day in the summer and 1040 liters (224 gallons) 2 times a day in the rainy season. A 20 liters bottle of this well is sold by 100 kyats in the quarters such as Yamanya and Aung Chantha. From this well, 16 water venders sell 28980 liters (6375 gallons) of water per day in the summer and 6440 liters (1417 gallons) a day in the rainy season.

There are 11 water venders in tube well No. 2 situated in ward No. 8 who sell 10800 liters (2376 gallons) of water every day with 9 carts 5 times a day in the summer and 4320 liters (950 gallons) 2 times a day in the rainy season. The water of this well is sold 6000 liters (1320 gallons) per day with three 30 bucket carts 5 times a day in the summer and 2400 liters (528 gallons) 2 times a day in the rainy season. A 20 liter bottle of this well is sold by 100 kyats in ward No. 8. From this well, 11 water venders sell 16800 liters (3696 gallons) of water per day in the summer and 6720 liters (1478 gallons) a day in the rainy season.

There is a water vender in tube well No. 3 which is situated in ward No. 8 who sells 1200 liters (264 gallons) 5 times a day with a 12 bucket cart to those who live in Yamanya and Aung Chantha quarters by 200 kyats a 5 gallon bottle in the summer.

There are 3 tube wells in ward No. 8 from which 28 water vendors distribute 46980 liters (10334 gallons) of drinking water in the summer and 73460 liters (16158 gallons) of drinking water to the customers every day.

Most of the brick lined wells are situated in ward Nos. 9 and 10, in the Western bank of the Patheingyi River. Water venders carry water and sell to the customers every day from the brick lined wells of these wards.

There are 7 brick lined wells in ward No. 9, in the Western bank of the Patheingyi River. These brick lined wells belong to the monastery. There are 5 brick lined wells in Seingone monastery, ward No. 9.

In Well No. 1 of Seingone monastery, there were 16 water venders and among them, 15 venders use carts and one vender uses trishaw to sell water. Each cart can carry 12 buckets containing 20 liters and a trishaw can carry 20 buckets of 20 liters. In the summer, 15 carts carry 25 times a day and distribute 75000 liters (16498 gallons) daily. A trishaw carries 25 times a day and distribute 10000 liters (2150 gallons) daily in the summer. In the rainy season, 15 carts carry 2 times a day and distribute 6000 liters (1320 gallons) daily. A trishaw carries 2 times a day and distribute 200 liters (176 gallons) daily in the rainy season. The price sold daily in ward No. 9 is 50 kyats for 20 liter bottle and 500 kyats for a cart. The 16 water venders of Seingone monastery well sell 85000 liters (18699 gallons) of water to the customers in the summer and 6200 liters (1364 gallons) in the rainy season every day.

There are 5 water venders in Well No.2 of Seingone monastery distributing 15 buckets of water in each cart. Water venders sell 15000 liters (3300 gallons) 15 times a day in the summer and 5000 liters (1100 gallons) 5 times a day in the rainy season. The price sold daily in ward No. 9 is 50 kyats for 20 liters. This well of 5 water venders sells 15000 liters (3300 gallons) of water to the customers in the summer and 5000 liters (1100 gallons) in the rainy season every day.

There are 6 water venders in Well No. 3 of Seingone monastery. In the summer, there are 4 carts each holding 12 buckets, carry 5 times a day and distribute 4800 liters (1056 gallons) daily and distributing 1920 liters (422 gallons) 2 times a day in the rainy season. In the summer, there are 2 carts each holding 10 buckets, carry 5 times a day and distribute 2000

liters (440 gallons) daily and distributing 800 liters (176 gallons) 2 times a day in the rainy season. The price sold daily in quarters such as Yekyaw, Thuhtay Kwatthitand Myaythada is 50 kyats to 100 kyats for a 20 liter bottle.

There are 6 water venders who sell 6800 liters (1496 gallons) daily in the summer and 2720 liters (598 gallons) a day in the rainy season from Well No. 3 of Seingone monastery. There are altogether 27 water venders who sell from 3 brick lined wells in ward No. 9 of Seingone monastery. They sell 106800 liters (23493 gallons) daily in the summer and 13920 liters (3062 gallons) a day in the rainy season.

There are brick -lined wells in Bgone monastery which is located in ward No. 9. Among them, only two wells are usable as drinking water and the rest one cannot be used since it is not qualified to be used as drinking water.

In Bogone Well No. 1, there are 6 water venders, 4 venders with carts and 2 with trishaw; selling 8640 liters (1900 gallons) of water every day with 4 carts each holding 12 buckets 9 times a day in the summer and 1920 liters (422 gallons) twice a day in the rainy season. In the summer, 3 trishaw each carrying 16 buckets, sell 5760 liters (1267 gallons) 9 times a day and 1280 liters (283 gallons) of water twice a day in the raining season. The price sold daily in Sandaraye quarter such as Nyaung Chaung, Thinbawkyin and Bogyoke Kwatthit is 100 kyats for a 20 liter bottle.

The 6 water venders from this well distribute 14400 liters (3168 gallons) of water in the summer and 3200 liters (704 gallons) a day in the rainy season.

In Bogone well No. 2, there are 11 water venders, selling 8960 liters (1971 gallons) of water every day with 8 carts each holding 14 buckets 4 times a day in the summer and 4480 liters (985 gallons) twice a day in the rainy season. In the summer, 3 trishaw each carrying 60 buckets, sell 14400 liters (3168 gallons) 4 times a day and 7200 liters (158 gallons) of water twice a day in the raining season. The price sold daily in ward No. 9 and ward No. 10 is 100 kyats for a 20 liter bottle.

The 11 water venders from this well distribute 23360 liters (5139 gallons) of water in the summer and 11680 liters (2569 gallons) a day in the rainy season.

In ward No. 9 Bogone monastery, there are 2 brick lined wells from which 17 water venders sell 37760 liters (8306 gallons) of water in the summer and 14880 liters (3273 gallons) in the rainy season every day.

In ward No. 9, there are 5 brick lined wells from which 44 water vendors sell 144160 liters (31800 gallons) of water in the summer and 28800 liters (6335 gallons) in the rainy season every day.

In ward No. 10, there are 4 brick-lined wells all of which situated in the monastery. There are 3 water venders in well No. 1, Gandaryone monastery of Ward No. 10, selling 1400 liters (317 gallons) of water every day with 3 carts each holding 12 buckets 2 times a day in the summer are 1400 liters (317 gallons) and 720 liters (158 gallons) one time a day in the rainy season. Depending on the distance, a 20 liter bottle is sold 50 to 100 kyats in ward No. 10. There are 3 water venders in this well, selling 1400 liters (317 gallons) of water every day and 720 liters (158 gallons) in the rainy season.

Well No. 2 of ward No. 10, situated in Theingone monastery, has 5 water venders selling 30000 liters (16599 gallons) of water every day with 5 carts each holding 20 buckets 15 times a day in the summer and 10000 liters (2200 gallons) 5 times a day in the rainy season. The price sold daily in Tarkaing, Mayanchaung, ShweKyiin Gone, Setkhalay and Quintan is 100 kyats for a 20 liter bottle. There are 5 water venders in this well, selling 30000 liters

(16599 gallons) of water every day in the summer and 10000 liters (2200 gallons) in the rainy season.

Brick-lined well No. 3 of ward No. 10, situated in Shwe Popa monastery, has 2 water vendors selling 4800liters (1056 gallons) of water every day with one cart each holding 16 buckets 15 times a day in the summer and 2560 liters (563 gallons) 8 times a day in the rainy season. And there is a cart holding 25 buckets that sells 7500 liters (1650 gallons) 15 times a day in the summer and 4000 liters (880 gallons) 15 times a day in the rainy season. Depending on the distance, a 20 liter bottle is sold 50 to 100 kyats in ward No. 9 and ward No. 10. The 2 water vendors of this well distribute 12300 liters (2706 gallons) per day in the summer and 6560 liters (1443 gallons) per day in the rainy season.

Brick-lined well No. 4 of ward No. 10, situated in Wartaw monastery, has 4 water vendors selling 4300 liters (1056 gallons) of water every day with 3 carts each holding 20 buckets 4 times a day in the summer and 2400 liters (528 gallons) 2 times a day in the rainy season. And there is a cart holding 40 buckets that sells 3200 liters (704 gallons) 4 times a day in the summer and 1600 liters (352 gallons) 2 times a day in the rainy season. Depending on the distance, a 20 liter bottle is sold 100 to 200 kyats in Setkhaly, Shwekyingone and Ye Ohsin. The 4water vendors of this well distribute 8000 liters (1759 gallons) per day in the summer and 4000 liters (880 gallons) per day in the rainy season.

In ward No. 10, there are 4 brick-lined wells from which 14 water vendors sell 64300 liters (14144 gallons) of water per day in the summer and 36280 liters (7981 gallons) a day in the rainy season as shown in Table (4.8).

In Pathein, the wards that lie on the East bank of the Ayeyawady river are ward Nos. 1, 2 ,4 ,5 ,6 ,7 ,8 ,11, 12, 13, 14 and 15. Among these wards, there are brick lined wells in ward Nos. 1, 2, 3 and 5.

There are 15 brick lined wells and 6 tube wells that supply drinking water in Pathein City. From these wells, 172 water vendors sell 471120 liters (103631 gallons) a day in the summer and 235500 liters (51802 gallons) a day in the rainy season.

Table 2. Daily amount of water sells by water vendors in Pathein City in 2015

Ward No.	Brick Lined Wells No./Name	Tube Wells No.	Water vendors	Liters		Total Production	
				Summer	Rainy	Summer	Rainy
1	Thit Nyogone	-	12	19200	4800	19200	4800
2	Shwehse gone	-	10	24000	12800	36400	19000
	KyaungThit	-	5	12400	6200		
3	B. E. H. S (II)	-	4	7200		7200	
5	Daw Ohn Myint	-	12	24000	14400	42000	19800
	U Maung Chit	-	9	18000	5400		

Ward No.	Brick Lined Wells No./Name	Tube Wells No.	Water vendors	Liters		Total Production	
				Summer	Rainy	Summer	Rainy
6	-	Tube well No. (1)	12	28800	9600	110880	40560
	-	Tube well No. (2)	7	28080	12960		
	-	Tube well No. (3)	15	54000	18000		
8	-	Tube well No. (1)	16	28980	6440	46980	13160
	-	Tube well No. (2)	11	16800	6720		
	-	Tube well No. (3)	1	1200	-		
9	Seingone (b.l.w) No. 1	-	16	85000	6200	144560	28800
	Seingone (b.l.w) No.2	-	5	15000	5000		
	Seingone (b.l.w)No.3	-	6	6800	2720		
	Bogone	-	6	14400	3200		
	Bogone	-	11	23360	11680		
10	Gandaryone	-	3	1400	720	51700	21280
	Theingone	-	5	30000	10000		
	Shwepopa	-	2	12300	6560		
	Wartaw	-	4	8000	4000		
Total		-	172	471120	235500	458920	147400

Source: Field Survey

Figure 4.1 Daily amount of water sells by water venders in Patheingyi City in 2015

Source: Base on Table 2

Summary

Currently, six purified drinking water plants and 172 water vendors play important role in drinking water supply in Patheingyi City. Water vendors take water from the wells (mostly shallow brick-lined wells) of monastery compound which are relatively good water quality and carry it in the polyethylene tanks and sell to the households. Many households have their own wells in their house but the water from most of them is not good quality water and it is not suitable for drinking purpose.

Therefore, majority of residents buy bottled water for drinking purpose and use the water from their wells for domestic use. Since the bottled water is very expensive (6 times more expensive than the water from water vendors), some of them use the water from the water vendors as the drinking water. If they do not have their own wells, they need to rely on the water from water vendors.

Low income population who cannot afford bottled water or the water from water vendors take themselves drinking water from ponds by buckets. Sometime they drink it without boiling. In test results of all water sources, high coliform count is found. The current condition of drinking water safety in Patheingyi City is very bad and the development of the water supply system is highly needed.

Acknowledgments

We would like to express our thanks to Dr. Aye Aye Tun, Rector and Dr. Yin Yin Than Pro-Rector, Bago University for their permission to present the research paper. We wish to express deepest thanks to Dr. Min Aung Pann, Professor and Head, Department of Geography, Bago University, for allowing me to undertake this paper and providing all the departmental facilities at my disposal. We wish to acknowledge to Dr. Mar Mar Khin, Professor, Department of Geography, Bago University, for her valuable suggestion. We also thank all the individuals from purified drinking water plants in Patheingyi City for their help during the collection of facts and figures.

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